

THE INFLUENCE OF INTERACTIVE JUSTICE ON EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT IN MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN RIVERS STATE

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Abstract: *The objective of the study was to examine the impact of interactive justice on employees' commitment, with focus on manufacturing firms in Rivers State. The study evaluates interactive justice as the dimension while the measures of employee commitment analyzed, are affective, normative, and continuance commitment. The explanatory cross-sectional survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consists of nineteen (19) registered manufacturing firms in Rivers State. For the purpose of fairness across the various firms the study adopted random sampling technique in which 10 employees were selected across the various 19 manufacturing firms which gave us a total of 190 respondents. The study adopted a primary source of data. Questionnaires were used to collect data from managers of the manufacturing firms in Rivers State. Structured questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. The research instrument was called "Interactive Justice questionnaire and Employee Commitment. Cronbach alpha was used to test the internal consistency of the instrument that was used for the study. The Cronbach's Alpha value is .877 indicating that the items are reliable hence they were accepted. The data collected from the administration of the instrument on the respondents were hand scored and entered on frequency tables in excel and exported to SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences. The Mean and standard deviations were used to analyses the research variables. Hypotheses were tested using Pearson's moment correlation statistics at 0.05 significance level. From the analysis of the study, the finding revealed that interactive justice has positive and significant relationship with affective, normative and continuance commitment. The study therefore, concluded that management abilities to foster good interpersonal relationship and effective channel of information to the employees would positively and significantly influence commitment in the organization. The study recommended that management in the Nigerian manufacturing sector should put in place a reward system that will be fair and just to the employees as it will boost the workers' morale to put more work effort and remain with the organization.*

Keywords: *Interactive Justice, Employee Commitment, Affective Commitment, Normative Commitment, Continuance Commitment and Manufacturing Firms.*

INTRODUCTION

Employees have been identified as one of the most important assets of successful organizations in today's emerging markets (Dossier, 1999). Committed employees bring about an increase in sale volume, affective commitment, effectiveness and efficiency. Varsha & Menika, (2012) emphasized that "in this era of digital revolution where competition is very high, employees are the most valuable resources in the hand of manage". For instance, finished goods can be delayed in the production centers if employees that is responsible for packaging it is not available to do so. Committed employees tend to have better attendance records and longer job tenure than less committed employees (Mowday, et al, 1982). Meyer & Allen (1990) also argued that committed employees tend to work harder at their jobs and perform better than do those with weak

commitment. In summary, there is considerable evidence that committed employees will be more valuable employees than those with weak commitment (Meyer & Allen, 1997). Some of the studies on employees' commitment are hereby presented with their findings. Varsha & Monika, (2012) identified the impact of employees' commitment on sustained affective commitment in auto-component industry

in India. The findings of the study indicate that the employees' commitment is significantly related to sustained affective commitment in auto component industry. Shane (2014) examined the relationship between servant leadership and employee Commitment to a supervisor. The study found that servant leadership has a significant effect on employee commitment to a supervisor.

Saraswathy, et al, (2014) examined the mediating role of employee commitment on the relationship between perceived supervisor support and role reversal among academic circle and practitioner in India. Employee commitment was found to partially mediate the relationship between perceived supervised support and role relevant. Wolfgang (2013) studied the effect of organizational culture on employee commitment in the India IT services sourcing industry.

Interactive justice is foster when decision makers treat people with respect and sensitivity as well as explain the rationale for decision thoroughly. It is a subset of procedural justice and refined into interpersonal justice and informational justice that focuses on dissemination of information about why procedures. Interactive justice is defined by sociologist Schermerhorn (2019) as the "degree to which the people affected by decision are treated by dignity and respect" in his organizational behavior theory he focused on the interpersonal treatment people receive when procedures are implemented.

The major components of interactive justice are interpersonal and informational justice. Interpersonal justice: This is the reflections of degree to which employees are treated with courtesy, dignity, and respect by management who determines employees' outcomes or implement organizational procedures.

Informational Justice: Informational component in interactive justice is focused on explanations provided to employees that convey information about why procedures used in a certain method. It refers to adequate explanation and rationale by management for the decision to distribute and process required for fairness of materials and retribution.

Interactive justice is the treatment that an individual or employee receives as decisions are made (Bies & Moag, 1986; Moorman, 1991 and Colquitt et al., 2001). Colquitt et al., (2001) suggested that interactive justice should be broken into two components namely interpersonal and informational justice. Bies & Moag (1986) identify some key aspects of interactive justice which can enhance people's perceptions of fair treatments. They are truthfulness (information given must be realistic and accurate, presented in an open and forth right manner), respect (employees treated with dignity, propriety (statements and questions should never be improper or involve prejudicial elements such as racism or sexism) and justification (when a perceived injustice has occurred giving explanation or apology can reduce or eliminate the sense of anger generated).

Bies & Moag (1986) introduced the concept of interactive justice. It is defined as "the quality of interpersonal treatment that people expect to receive when procedures are implemented" and emphasizes "the importance of true, fulness, respect and justification as fairness criteria of interpersonal communication" (Bies & Moag, 1986 & Dies,-) Thus, interactive justice deals with the human side of organizational practices and, as such is related in the communication aspects between the source and recipient of justice, such as politeness, honesty and respect (Bies & Moag, 1986).

According to Masterson et al, (2000); Cohen-Charish & Spelcer, (2002). Interactive justice refers to perceptions concerning the way authorities treat their subordinates respond to these perceptions. This is related to the quality of relationship between individuals within the organizations (Folger & Cropanzano, 1998).

In interactive justice, decision makers treatment of those affected by decisions is crucial because people identify attitudes as indicators of justice within the organization. Employee, are sensitive to the communications they receive regarding the implementations of procedure and the explanations of decisions (Karriker and Williams, 2009). It refers to perceptions concerning the way authorities treat their subordinates, and know these subordinates respond to these perceptions (Masterson et al, 2000; Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2007).

"Specifically., while most employees are happy with their communities to work and their relationships with colleagues, they are most, dissatisfied with their companies' 'bonus plans', promotion policies, health plans, and pensions. With respect to management, 40% of workers feel disconnected from their employers' and less than one out of three supervisors and managers are viewed as being good leaders. However, more and more employers today are finding that employees stay between 23 to 24 months with their organizations" (U.S Bureau of Labour Statistics, 2008).

An organization that has greater ability of employee commitment, is an employee-friendly organization and it is critical to the going concern of the organization. Employee commitment, according to Meyer and Allen: 1991) is state of mind that characterizes the employees' relationship with the organization which has implications for the decision to remain or leave the organization. They formed a three-component model of commitment which has been well-researched and is widely used by the academic community. The three-dimensional constructs are affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment.

Affective commitment refers to emotional attachment, identification with, and involvement that an employee has with his or her organization and goals. (Meyer & Allen, 1997). Continuance commitment refers to commitment based on the costs that the employee associates with leaving the organization (Meyer and Allen, 1997). Normative commitment is the commitment based on reciprocity or the feeling of obligation by the employee to the organization (Bolon, 1997).

The importance of employee commitment has been highlighted by a lot of studies (Gbadamosi, 2003; Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002; Farndale et al, 2011; Ahiauzu & Asawo, 2008) among others. Gbadamosi (2003) reported that employee commitment continues to be an unavoidable issue in management research and continues to engage the attention of practicing managers.' Rhoades & Eisenberger (2002) contended that those employees who feel that they are looked for by their organizations not only show high level of commitment but are more conscious about their roles, thus put greater impact in actualization of the organization's objectives, and are more innovative in carrying out their duties. Farndale et al, (2011) believed that commitment is an important factor in trying to achieve longer term organizational goals. Employee commitment enhances performance and organizational effectiveness (Zabid et al., 2003). Employee commitment has positive relationship with intention to stay and increases performance (Angler and Perry, 1981). Employees commitment at work place produces a healthy organizational climate, increased morale and motivates staff productivity (Salami, 2008). Luchak & Gellatly (2007) in their study found that commitment to work triggers better performance among workforce. "When affective commitment is low, absenteeism and turnover will be high" according to the findings of Pare & Tremblay (2007). Meyer & Allen (1996) also found that lack of commitment to organizational goals leads to high turnover intention and actual turnover in work place. Owing to the importance attached to employee commitment, there have been several studies which examined its impact on achieving organizational goals;'. For instance, Ahiauzu & Asawo (2009) studied

the impact of altruistic love as an element in the emerging theme of workplace spirituality and employee commitment in the Nigerian manufacturing industry. In their study, they found out that employee affectivity is significantly influenced by spirituality at work place. Ogba (2009) examined the impact of income and age on employee commitment and found out that income and age influenced normative and continuance commitments respectively. Gbadamosi (2003) highlighted contemporary issues in employee commitment as it relates to human resource management. Therefore, this study is intended to add to knowledge by examining the impact of interactive justice on employee's commitment of manufacturing firms in Rivers State.

A major problem facing most manufacturing firms in Nigerian is how to get the commitment of employees. Lack of commitment is manifested in various manufacturing firms through absenteeism, high labour turnover, low morale, lack of focus, failure to meet targets in job duties, poor attitude to work, and so on. These problems can be attributed by lack of fairness from management to the employees. Relating how much employee absenteeism can cost an employer the Nigerian government released a report in June, 2013 indicating that Federal Civil Servants missed work an average of 18 days per year in Nigeria, which amounts to more than N600 Billion (S3 Billion) in lost wages a year. Despite this exorbitant number, it is to be noted that it only considers the direct cost of absenteeism and would be much greater if the indirect costs could be identified (Vourcnsyrja, 2003, in Chris, 2013). Also, a recent survey conducted by Career Builders, showed that 15% of workers are absent from work at least once a week. The number is up from 16% in 2008 and 20% in 2009. The analysis in their survey showed that the total cost of absenteeism for the period was N56Millioi: (US \$800,018). The yearly average cost was N26million (US \$400,009). According to Linda (2013), unscheduled absenteeism and lateness to work rates have risen to high levels in the workplace in recent year and this has continued to be of great concern to employers, who view the practices as counter-productive. More worrisome is the fact that many of the best employees are not in their places of work at 8:00am when they are expected to resume work.

All over the world there is total agreement about the fallen standard of workers' attitude (Adebule, 2004), Shareholders are in unanimity that their huge investments on organizations are not yielding the desired dividends. Customers also complain of workers' poor attitude at both within and outside the organizations. Aremu (2010, in Wasilu, 2013) stressed that attitude is not only frustrating to the owners and the customers, its effects are equally grave on the society in terms of dearth of man power in all spheres of the economy and politics,

Nigeria is no exception, and required enhancing work attitude for productivity. Okorie (2000) advised the need to remove the main obstacles in indigenous workers' general attitude to work and working relationship with others. Some of those deficiencies, according to him, include: lack of initiative, inadequate management training, and poor relationship with workers, reluctance to do manual work, inadequate educational or professional background, and 'insufficient loyalty to enterprise. These are likely to have adverse effect on workers' productivity and retard industrial progress in the country.

Since manufacturing sector is a major target of Nigeria's economy, concern is raised as to why there is low productivity in the sector. Although, it is a fact that the manufacturing sector is growing very fast, providing services and opportunities of employment, however there are some psychological and material problems such as fairness to employees, workers' alienation, unfair pay and casualization of workers which ha\u degenerated into corporate reputation failure, job dissatisfaction, turnover

intention, high turnover rate, brain drain, employee' cynicism, and so on, which may limit the growth of the industry, therefore call for attention.

Studies conducted in some parts of Euro, America, Asia, and so on, as discussed above, have shown that interactive justice is important for effective management technique and can address employee's commitment, satisfaction, and intention to stay with the organization. Previous empirical works, such as (Ahiauzu, 1999; Ahiauzu & Asawo, 2009; Ogba, 2009; Gbadamosi, 2003; Aluko et al, 1998; Baridam, 2002; Baridam & Nwibere, 2008; found that quality of working-life, job satisfaction, motivation, and so on, have positive relationships with employee commitment.

Little is known at present about the influence of interactive justice on employee commitment in Rivers State work settings. The study is intended to explore the extent to which interactive justice influences employee commitment in manufacturing firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Aim and Objective of the Study

The main aim of this study was to examine the relationship between interactive justice and employee commitment in manufacturing firms in Rivers State.

Specifically, the objectives of the study are to;

1. examine the relationship between interactive justice and affective commitment in manufacturing firms in Rivers State.
2. investigate the relationship between interactive justice and normative commitment in manufacturing firms in Rivers State.
3. ascertain the relationship between interactive justice and continuance commitment in manufacturing firms in Rivers State.

Research Questions

Based on the objectives of this study, the following research questions will be addressed:

1. What is the relationship between interactive justice and affective commitment in manufacturing firms in Rivers State?
2. How does interactive justice relate with normative commitment in manufacturing firms in Rivers State?
3. To what extent does interactive justice relate to continuance commitment in manufacturing firms in Rivers State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses shall be tested in this study;

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between interactive justice and affective communication in manufacturing firms Rivers State.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between interactive justice and normative commitment in manufacturing firms in Rivers State.

HO₃: There is no significant relationship between interactive justice and continuance commitment in manufacturing firms in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The explanatory cross-sectional survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consists of nineteen (19) registered manufacturing firms in Rivers State. For the purpose of fairness across the various firms the study adopted random sampling technique in which 10 employees were selected across the various nineteen (19) manufacturing firms which gave us a total of 190

respondents. The study adopted a primary source of data. Primarily, structured questionnaires were used to collect data from managers of the manufacturing firms in Rivers State. The research instrument was called “Interactive Justice questionnaire and Employee Commitment. Cronbach alpha was used to test the internal consistency of the instrument that was used for the study. The Cronbach's Alpha value is .877 indicating that the items are reliable hence they were accepted. The data collected from the administration of the instrument on the respondents were hand scored and entered on frequency tables in excel and exported to SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences. The Mean and standard deviations were used to analyses the research variables. Hypotheses were tested using Pearson’s moment correlation statistics at 0.05 significance level.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Univariate Analysis

Table 1, Statistics on Interactive Justice

	u_i	1 UL2	IJ_3
N Valid	300	300	300
Missing	0	0	0
Mean	3.98	3.98	3.97
Std. Deviation	.938	.894	1.029
Variance	.879	.799	1.059
Skewness	-1.045	-.731	-.885
Std. Error of Skewness	.141	.141	.141
Minimum	1	1	1
Maximum	5	5	5

Source; SPSS Computation 2024

Table 1, the frequency distribution showing worker's response to the items on interactive justice. Employees reported that there are human relations on the organization with mean value of 3.98 as moderate. Respondents affirmed that there Is adequate information dissemination on the organization with a moderate mean value of 3.98. Respondents agreed that there is team work between employees on the organization with a moderate mean value of 3.97.

Affective Commitment

Table 2, Statistics on Affective commitment

	AC_1	AC=2	AC3
N Valid	300	300	300
Missing	0	0	0
Mean	3.86	4.11	3.91
Std. Deviation	.906	.859	.902
Variance	.821	.738	.814

Skewness	-1.004	-.940	-.805
Std. Error of Skewness	.141	.141	.141
Minimum	1	1	1
Maximum	5	5	5

Source: SPSS Computation 2024

Table 2, is the frequency distribution showing responses to the items on the research instrument on affective commitment. Participants agreed that the organization has good reputation with moderate mean value of 3.86, Respondents agreed that there is citizenship behaviour of the employees on the organization, this item had a very high mean value of 4.11. Employees agreed that in their organization there is love and oneness, with mean value of 3.91 as moderate

Normative Commitment

Table 3, Statistics on Normative Commitment

	NC_1	NC_2	NC_3	NC_4
N Valid	300	300	300	3DO
Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean	4.02	3.92	3.83	3.91
Std. Deviation	.945	.952	.964	.974
Variance	.893	.908	.929	.949
Skewness	-.967	-.957	-.676	-.678
Std. Error of Skewness	.141	.141	.141	.141
Minimum	1	1	1	1
Maximum	5	5	5	5

Source: SPSS Computation 2024

Table 3, is a frequency distribution on the items measuring normative commitment. In response to item one, participants agreed that there is support from the organization with a very high mean score of 4.02. Employees believe in the importance of loyalty therefore feel moral obligation to remain with their organizations. This item has a moderate mean score of 3.92. Employees agreed that the organizations were able to meet the financial obligation, this has a mean score of 3.83. The next item also has a moderate mean value of 3.91, implying that employees agreed with the statement that they were taught to believe in the value of remaining loyal to one organization and wanting to be a company man or woman is sensible

Continuance Commitment

Table 4, Statistics on Continuance Commitment

	CC_1	CC_2	CC_3
N Valid	300	300	300
Missing	0	0	0
Mean	3.82	3.86	3.84
Std. Deviation	1.038	1.007	.994
Variance	1.078	1.015	.989
Skewness	-.753	-.731	-.626
Sid. Error of Skewness	.141	.141	.141
Minimum	1	1	1
Maximum	5	5	5

Source: SPSS Computation 2024

Table 4, is a frequency distribution showing responses on the items measuring continuance commitment in the instrument. In response to item one, employees mean score was 3.82 which is moderate showing that they agreed with the statement that they are satisfied with their job. Employees agreed to the next statement that it will be too costly to leave the organization due to spirit of common purpose and sense of belonging with mean value of 3.86. Workers agreed that they have the obligation to remain with the organization due to the commitment and motivation from the management, this item has a moderate mean value of 3.84.

Bivariate Analysis

Research Hypotheses

Table 5, H₀₁ Correlations

	Interactive commitment	Affective justice
Spearman's rho INTER: Correlation ACTlONAL JUSTICE Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed) N	1.000 300	.373 .000 300
AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT EN Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.373 300	1.000 .000 300

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The seventh hypothesis testing the relationship between work-life balance and affective commitment shows there is a positive relationship existing between them with a correlation coefficient of .373 and a p-value of .000 which is also less than alpha (0.05) we therefore reject the null hypothesis.

Table 6, Ho₂ Correlations

			Interactive	Normative commitment
Spearman's rho	INTERACTIVE	Correlation	1.000	.392
JUSTICE		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
		N	300	300
Spearman's rho	NORMATIVE	Correlation	.392	1.000
COMMITMENT	TME	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
		N	300	300

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Our eighth hypothesis also shows a significant correlation coefficient of .392 and a p-value of .000 which is less than alpha (.05) we therefore reject the null hypothesis which implies that there is a positive relationship existing between interactive justice and normative commitment.

Table 7, Ho₃ Correlations

			Interactive justice	Continuance commitment
Spearman's rho	INTERACTIVE	Correlation	1.000	.431
JUSTICE		Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
		N	300	300
Spearman's rho	CONTINUANCE	Correlation	.431	1.000
COMMITMENT		Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
		N	300	300

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The hypothesis testing the relationship between work-life balance and continuance commitment shows a correlation coefficient of .431 and a p-value of .000 which is less than our alpha value (.05) therefore we reject the null hypothesis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Every sustainable organization improves on her interactive justice to employees, which will enhance employee commitment and performance. This justice system is seen as motivational strategies to enthuse employees to put more work efforts and have sense of belonging to the organization.

We have found out in this study that interactive justice is a strong motivational technique to employee commitment in the manufacturing sector of Nigeria economy.

The first to the three hypotheses examined the relationship between interactive justice and employee commitment. Hence, it was hypothesized that;

There are no significant relationships between interactive justice and affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment.

Data analysis ($r=0.373$, $p<0.05$; $r=0.392$, $p<0.05$; $r=0.431$, $p<0.05$) indicated that a positive and significant relationships exist between interactive justice and affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment to the organization.

From the data analysis above and findings, we counter the previous null hypotheses that there are no significant relationships between interactive justice and affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment to there are significant relationships between interactive justice and affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment.

Based on the above findings, it was concluded that interactive justice, influenced affective commitment, normative commitment and continuance commitment to the organization. These findings are in line with the earlier work on interactive justice and employee commitment by various authors.

Bakshi, et al (2009) asserted that interactive justice was significantly correlated with the organizational commitment of the employed in India.

Meckenna (2005) asserted that by employees' participating, being involved and making suggestions in the organization make them affectively committed to the organization.

Pauline, et al, (2005) pointed out that when workplace conditions are supportive and equitable, it will create affective commitment.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above findings, it was concluded that interactive justice, influenced affective commitment, normative commitment and continuance commitment to the organization. Management ability to foster good interpersonal relationship and effective channel of information (interactive justice) to the employees would positively and significantly influence affective, normative, and continuance commitment to the organization.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were given below in this study;

1. The positive and significant relationships between interactive justice and employees' commitment suggest that management in the Nigerian manufacturing sector should put in place a reward system that will be fair and just to the employees as it will boost the workers' morale to put more extra work effort and remain with the organization.
2. Management should proffer appropriate methods of allocating process that would be consistent, accurate and un-bias in allocation of resources and justice delivery to the employees. Effective interactive justice will bring about trust and commitment of the employees to the organization.
3. Management should provide an appropriate means and manners for interacting and disseminating information to the employees, hence effective interactive justice will enhance team work, collaboration and social inclusiveness that led to commitment to the organization.

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